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To cite this article: Irem Unalan *et al* 2024 *Biomed. Mater.* **19** 065001

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RECEIVED
31 May 2024

REVISED
22 July 2024

ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
16 August 2024

PUBLISHED
3 September 2024

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Cotton wool-like ion-doped bioactive glass nanofibers: investigation of Zn and Cu combined effect

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Keywords: cotton wool-like electrospun nanofibers, sol–gel synthesis, zinc, copper, wound healing

Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Electrospinning is a versatile and straightforward technique to produce nanofibrous mats with different morphologies. In addition, by optimizing the solution, processing, and environmental parameters, three-dimensional (3D) nanofibrous scaffolds can also be created using this method. In this work, the preparation and characterization of bioactive glass (BG) scaffolds based on the SiO₂–CaO sol–gel system, a biomaterial with a highly reactive surface, is reported. The electrospinning technique was combined with sol–gel methods to obtain nanofibrous 3D cotton wool-like scaffolds. The addition of zinc and copper ions to the silica–calcia system was examined, and the influence of these ions on the material properties and characteristics was investigated by various characterization techniques, from morphological and chemical properties to antibacterial and wound closure capability, cell viability and ion release. Our findings show that the cotton wool-like ion-doped nanofibers are promising for wound healing applications.

1. Introduction

The skin is the largest organ in the human body, and it can sustain damage from burns, trauma, surgery, or lacerations. Traditional approaches to address such complications have often proven ineffective. Consequently, the field of wound care has seen the emergence of innovative technologies like nanofiber scaffolds, which facilitate skin tissue engineering and offer improved treatment options for various skin lesions [1].

Wound healing encompasses the intricate physiological response of a living system to thermal, mechanical, physical, or chemical injuries. It involves the coordinated efforts of cells, scaffolds, and various biological factors to restore damaged tissue integrity promptly and promote functional and aesthetic recovery. To achieve successful wound healing, several

critical characteristics must be addressed. These include maintaining an optimal moisture level in the wound bed, accommodating different wound types and body regions, regulating temperature, facilitating gaseous exchange, preventing microbial colonization (with antibacterial properties), ensuring biocompatibility, enabling controlled release of therapeutic agents, demonstrating non-toxicity, achieving high reproducibility, and providing mechanical stability, among others [2].

When nanometer-scale scaffolds are fabricated, new properties emerge, such as stronger mechanical capacities, lighter and more porous structures, and other significant changes related to chemical reactivity, electronic and magnetic properties, and even the appearance of new functionalities. Over the last decades, the development of porous scaffolds has been an intensive area of research. The concept of nanofibers

and their manufacture, along with the appropriate production method and the correct selection of materials, has emerged. Then, the composition, structure, and properties of nanofibers can be engineered to target specific applications [3]. Biocompatible polymeric and/or bioceramic scaffolds can provide architectural, surface, and compositional characteristics, including biodegradability, mechanical stability, porosity, and large surface-to-volume ratio for designing advanced wound healing devices [4].

Bioactive glasses (BGs) are suitable materials for such applications. BGs can be defined as non-crystalline inorganic materials that have the ability to bond to living tissue and stimulate new tissue growth as they degrade over time [5]. One of the most commonly developed systems is based on SiO_2 -CaO with the addition of different ions that allow obtaining specific properties for certain applications, such as Ag, Cu, and Zn, with antibacterial properties [6].

Tissue engineering applications require suitable scaffolds with morphological and chemical similarity to the extracellular matrix of natural tissue. These scaffolds should have a high surface area-to-volume ratio and interconnected porosity. In particular, electrospun BG nanofibrous scaffolds offer numerous advantages for wound healing applications, where short recovery times are required [3, 7]. For instance, Poologasundarampillai *et al* [8] reported the production of electrospun three-dimensional (3D) cotton wool-like scaffolds composed of 70 mol.% SiO_2 and 30 mol.% CaO through a combination of sol-gel and electrospinning. These sol-gel-derived inorganic materials exhibited bioactivity and no adverse cytotoxic effect when cultured with MC3T3-E1 preosteoblast cells. In another study, Norris *et al* investigated the formation of electrospun BG scaffolds with different Si/Ca molar ratios [5]. The authors found that compositions containing 70:30 and 80:20 Si/Ca were suitable for wound healing applications. Samples presented a rapid release of silicon and calcium and did not inhibit the expression of VEGF from CD-18CO cells over 7 d. In a similar study, Sengupta *et al* [9] reported that borosilicate (60SiO_2 - 20CaO - $16\text{B}_2\text{O}_3$ - $4\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$) glass fibers exhibit mineralization ability. Additionally, their dissolution products were found to be non-cytotoxic for mouse osteoblast and fibroblast cell lines, depending on the concentration used [9].

On the other hand, a variety of therapeutic inorganic ions can also be incorporated into BG networks to modify and enhance their specific properties [10]. In this regard, several therapeutic inorganic ions have been studied for wound healing applications, including silver, magnesium, zinc, strontium, copper, gallium, and boron [11]. Among them, zinc and copper ions play crucial roles in various physiological processes in the body [11–13]. For instance, Quirós *et al*

[14] reported that electrospun polyvinylpyrrolidone nanofibers containing silver, copper, or zinc nanoparticles showed high antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. In another study, Chhabra *et al* [15] found that nano zinc oxide-doped nanofibrous scaffolds of gelatin and poly-methyl vinyl ether-alt-maleic anhydride (PMVE/MA) promoted faster wound healing in normal Swiss albino mice compared to electrospun fibers without zinc oxide [15]. Recently, Liverani *et al* reported the fabrication of electrospun Cu-doped BG cotton wool-like nanofibrous scaffolds for wound healing applications [16]. The addition of copper showed reduced mineralization upon immersion in SBF, while cytocompatibility and wound closure rate were not affected by Cu release.

Despite the research on Cu-doped BG electrospun fibers [16], to the best of the authors' knowledge, the effect of various concentrations of Zn, Cu, and their combinations, specifically for the synergistic effect of Zn and Cu, in BG electrospun fibers has not yet been studied. Therefore, this study aims to fabricate BG electrospun fibers incorporated with Zn, Cu, or a combination of Zn/Cu for wound healing applications. In this regard, the combination of the electrospinning technique with the sol-gel process was used to obtain a series of fibrous structures based on SiO_2 -CaO doped with Zn, Cu, or Zn/Cu ions. The electrospinning parameters, as well as environmental parameters and composition, were the determining factors for obtaining 3D cotton wool-like structures. Special emphasis was placed on the addition of zinc and copper ions to the SiO_2 -CaO system, where the influence of these ions on the properties and characteristics of the nanofibers was studied. These ion releasing cotton wool-like structures are of particular interest in wound healing applications.

2. Materials and methods

Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, $\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany) and used as a precursor alkoxide for the sol-gel process. Nitric acid (HNO_3) was purchased from VWR and utilized as a catalyst to obtain silicon dioxide (SiO_2) from TEOS. Additionally, ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) was added to the solution as a solvent required for electrospinning.

To form the silica-calcia system, calcium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was incorporated into the solution. In order to obtain a desired viscosity for the subsequent electrospinning process, polyvinyl butyral (PVB) was added as a binding agent. Finally, zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and copper nitrate hemi (pentahydrate) ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were added to incorporate the desired ion concentrations. All the components were added using a magnetic stirrer. PVB was used as a binding agent due to its excellent adhesive properties, ability to enhance mechanical strength, and compatibility with

Table 1. Compositions for solution preparation.

Composition	TEOS (ml)	HNO ₃ (ml)	EtOH (ml)	Ca(NO ₃) ₂ · 4H ₂ O (g)	Zn(NO ₃) ₂ · 6H ₂ O (g)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ · 2.5H ₂ O (g)	H ₂ O (ml)
80Si–20Ca	4.1	0.95	2.1	2.18	—	—	0.15
80Si–18Ca–2Zn	4.1	0.95	2.1	1.95	0.27	—	0.15
80Si–18Ca–2Cu	4.1	0.95	2.1	1.95	0	0.21	0.15
80Si–16Ca–2Zn–2Cu	4.1	0.95	2.1	1.74	0.27	0.21	0.15
80Si–15Ca–5Zn	4.1	0.95	2.1	0.82	0.34	—	0.15
80Si–15Ca–5Cu	4.1	0.95	2.1	0.82	0	0.27	0.15
80Si–10Ca–5Zn–5Cu	4.1	0.95	2.1	0.54	0.34	0.27	0.15
80Si–10Zn–10Cu	4.1	0.95	2.1	—	0.68	0.54	0.15

a variety of plasticizers [16]. All salts were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany).

Different compositions were formulated by varying amounts of zinc, copper, and calcium ions. Table 1 summarizes the composition of the studied solutions and the amount of each reagent used in each fabricated scaffold. The amount of PVB in all compositions was 0.15 g (5% w/v).

After 48 h from the addition of the last precursor, the sols were prepared for electrospinning. Separately, each solution was loaded into a 3 ml Henke-Ject syringe fitted with a 21 G needle. The syringe was then secured to the pump and stabilized using tape. The flow rate was set to 0.5 ml h⁻¹. The collector, covered with aluminum foil, was positioned in front of the needle, maintaining a distance of 12 cm between the needle tip and the collector. A voltage of 15 kV was applied to the needle using the Starter Kit from Linari Engineering SRL (Pisa, Italy). All electrospinning parameters were set based on the research conducted by Norris *et al* [5] and Liverani *et al* [16]. Throughout the production process, temperature and relative humidity (RH) were monitored. The electrospun fibers underwent a heat treatment (HT) involving calcination in a Nabertherm P330 muffle furnace. The fibers were placed in suitable ceramic containers and heated at a rate of 1 °C min⁻¹ until reaching a temperature of 600 °C.

2.1. Morphology and physical structure

In order to study the functional groups, infrared spectroscopy was conducted using a Shimadzu IRAffinity-1S Fourier-transformed infrared spectrophotometer with attenuated total reflectance mode (ATR-FTIR). Absorbance mode was used with a total of 40 scans per sample, a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, Happ-Genzel type apodization (to reduce ripples), and a wavenumber range between 400 cm⁻¹ and 4000 cm⁻¹. Characterization of all compositions was performed both before and after the HT. The morphology and microstructural characteristics were analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). An Auriga-Base 0750 equipment from Zeiss, Germany, was used to examine samples, with a voltage acceleration of 1 kV and a variable working distance depending on

the sample (ranging from 2.5–6 mm). High-quality micro-scale images were obtained, and the diameter of the fibers was analyzed before and after the calcination HT using ImageJ software (50 fibers per composition) [17].

Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was performed using the same equipment to determine the chemical elements present in the cotton wool-like BG samples and their respective relative concentrations. This technique also allowed the analysis of the spatial distribution of elements by generating color maps of specific regions in the selected samples. A voltage acceleration of 20 kV was applied, and the working distance was adjusted according to the sample being analyzed (ranging from 5–6 mm). The EDX study was performed only after HT.

2.2. Ion release

The dissolution and concentration profiles of the Ca, Si, Cu, and Zn ions were measured with slight modification according to Norris *et al* [5]. Briefly, the 10 mg of cotton wool-like fibers samples were placed in 6.67 ml TRIS (5 mM, pH ~ 7.4 at 37 °C, Carl Roth GmbH, Karlsruhe Germany) and stored in an incubator shaker at 37 °C and 120 rpm. At each time point (4 h, 1, 3, and 7 d), 0.8 ml of TRIS supernatant from each sample was collected and filtered with a 0.22 µm syringe filter (Carl Roth GmbH, Germany). Afterward, the supernatants were mixed with 4.2 ml of fresh TRIS and 0.1 ml of 1 M nitric acid (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Finally, samples were analyzed using optical emission spectroscopy with inductively coupled plasma (ICP-OES, Varian MPX) analysis at wavelengths of 396.847 nm (Ca²⁺) and 288.158 nm (Si⁴⁺), 327.395 nm (Cu²⁺) and 213.857 nm (Zn²⁺). A series of at least three calibration solutions was prepared to obtain a linear correlation between the intensity of ions and concentration. The internal standardization technique with scandium (10 mg l⁻¹) as the internal standard was used to deal with non-spectral interferences. The precision of the analysis for all ions expressed as the relative standard deviation was below 5%. The measurements were made in triplicate for all compositions after HT. The average

values including standard deviations from three replicates for each dissolved ion were reported.

2.3. Antibacterial properties

The antibacterial activity of the cotton wool-like scaffolds was tested against the gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and the gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*, as it was the intention to investigate this characteristic in relation to the amount of Zn or Cu ions present in the nanofibers. In this regard, firstly, the scaffolds were sterilized under UV irradiation for 30 min on each side. Meanwhile, bacterial colonies were incubated in 10 ml of Luria/Miller medium (LB medium; Carl Roth, Germany) at 37 °C for 24 h. The optical density of the bacterial population was then calibrated to a value of 0.001 nm at 600 nm using a Thermo Scientific™ GENESYS 30™ spectrophotometer (Germany), following the measurement of the culture bacterial turbidity. Subsequently, inoculum of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* was added to each cotton wool-like fibers (1 mg ml⁻¹) and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. The metabolic activity of bacteria was assessed by adding AlamarBlue® (Invitrogen, United States) after 24 h following the manufacturer's protocol for incubation.

Moreover, the viability of the incubated bacteria in contact with the samples was evaluated using agar plates (LB Agar; Carl Roth, Germany). After plating 100 µl of supernatant onto agar plates, the growth of bacteria was observed after 24 h of incubation at 37 °C. As a control, bacteria were cultured without scaffolds. These experiments were conducted in triplicate for all compositions, specifically after the HT. Subsequently, absorbance measurements at 570 nm and 600 nm were taken (a region of interest for this type of bacteria), and the reduction of AlamarBlue was calculated [18].

2.4. Cell studies: *in vitro* cytotoxicity assay

The indirect cell viability assay was performed per the ISO-10993-5 standard test method [19]. Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM, 31885–023), penicillin/streptomycin (PS, 15140–122), and trypsin/EDTA (25200–056) were purchased from Thermo Scientific (Schwerte, Germany). Human keratinocyte cells (HaCaT, CAS number 300493) were ordered from Cell lines service. HaCaT cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and 1% PS in 75 cm² cell culture flasks (Nunc, Denmark). Subsequently, the HaCaT cells were detached by trypsinization and counted by trypan blue assay using a hemocytometer (Roth, Germany). Counted cells were seeded in 24-well plates at 100.000 cells well⁻¹ density and incubated at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ for 24 h. Before the cell culture experiments, the cotton wool-like fibers were sterilized by UV light irradiation for 30 min for each side. Then, to prepare

the extract medium sample, cotton wool-like fibers (1 mg ml⁻¹) were submerged in the cell medium for 24 h at 37 °C. Afterward, the cells were incubated with these extracted solutions for another 48 h. After 48 h of incubation, the cells were treated with 1% (v/v) WST-8 diluted by a related cell medium. Finally, the absorbance was measured after 3 h of incubation at 450 nm by a microplate reader, and the cell viability was calculated as reported elsewhere [20]. The measurements were done for all compositions after HT.

2.5. *In vitro* wound healing assay

The *in vitro* wound healing assay was carried out according to the procedure described elsewhere [20]. Firstly, HaCaT cells were seeded at 100 000 cells well⁻¹ into a 24-well plate and were incubated at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ for 24 h. Then, a vertical scratch was created in the HaCaT monolayer's surface using a 100 µl sterile pipet tip. After 24 h incubation, the medium in each well was exchanged with extractions of cotton wool-like fibers (1 ml) mentioned above. Finally, the wound closure rate was monitored at different times (0 h, 4 h, and 24 h) and captured using a light microscope (Primo Vert, Carl Zeiss). The images were analyzed with Image J (NIH, Bethesda, MD, USA). The rate of wound closure was calculated using the corresponding formula [20]. The measurements were done for all compositions in triplicate after HT.

2.6. Statistical analysis

In all the experiments, to analyze the statistical significance, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the Bonferroni test at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$ was performed using Origin (Origin Lab, Northampton, MA, USA). The results were denoted as mean ± standard deviation (SD).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Cotton wool-like scaffolds fabrication

Overall, the fabrication process for all cotton wool-like electrospun BG compositions was successful. The electrospinning parameters remained unchanged during the fabrication of nanofibers. However, for certain compositions (80Si–20Ca and 80Si–15Ca–5Cu), the desired 3D structure could not be achieved, resulting in the formation of two-dimensional (2D) films instead. Although the processing parameters were constant, variations in RH were observed while the ambient temperature remained relatively consistent. The average RH measured for all compositions was 28.8% ± 3.1%, with an average temperature of 23 °C ± 1 °C. For the 80Si–20Ca composition, the RH values were in the range 27%–37%, which could have a detrimental effect on the three-dimensionality of the scaffolds [5]. In the case of 80Si–15Ca–5Cu,

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of cotton wool-like scaffolds: (A) 80Si-20Ca before HT (left side: 10 000 \times , right side (5000 \times), (B) 80Si-20Ca after HT, (C) 80Si-15Ca-5Cu before HT, (D) 80Si-16Ca-2Zn-2Cu after HT.

the RH was 26%–28%, and occasional 2D films were observed. These difficulties were minimal as they only occurred for a few minutes during the fabrication of two compositions, while the rest did not encounter any issues. However, it is important to consider RH as a significant factor affecting the macrostructure of nanofiber scaffolds obtained by electrospinning [5, 16].

Another factor that could compromise the three-dimensionality of the cotton wool-like scaffolds was the absence of Ca^{2+} ions in the solution. The presence of these ions increases the charge density on the surface of the jet, allowing for the branching of nanofibers and the formation of 3D structures [8]. In a previous study reported by Poologasundarampillai *et al* [8], who investigated the effect of calcium nitrate incorporation into the BG electrospun solution, it was found that 3D cotton-wool-like structures were only produced when solutions containing calcium nitrate were used [8]. In contrast to their study, in this study, the 80Si-10Zn-10Cu composition was able to produce 3D cotton-wool-like structures even

without calcium in the SiO_2 -CaO system. This could be attributed to binding mechanisms between the silicon dioxide (SiO_2) and the zinc and copper ions that facilitate the formation of covalent bonds [13], resulting in structural integrity, mechanical strength, and chemical stability of the ion doped 3D cotton-wool-like structure.

3.2. Fiber morphology

Figure 1(A) shows SEM images of 80Si-20Ca (reference case) before HT. It can be observed that a network of entangled nanofibers is formed. Some fibers, however, remain attached and do not fully separate from each other. Additionally, the nanofibers appear homogeneous and free of bead-like agglomerations. Figure 1(B) displays the same nanofibers after the calcination HT, during which the PVB component was removed from the sample. It can be confirmed that the fiber morphology remains unaltered, and no changes in the macrostructure were observed. The SEM image also revealed the presence of interconnected fibers and occasional cross-cut fibers. On the

Figure 2. Nanofiber diameters of the studied cotton wool-like scaffolds.

other hand, incorporating copper in 80Si–15Ca–5Cu did not introduce significant changes in the fibrous morphology (figure 1(C)). It is worth noting that during the preparation of the solution, the procedures were different, as occasional difficulties were encountered in dissolving the PVB (taking 1–2 h). This prolonged sol–gel stage could affect the final viscosity of the solution and contribute to the occasional bead formation [5, 21].

A SEM micrograph of 80Si–16Ca–2Zn–2Cu scaffolds after the HT is depicted in figure 1(D). The addition of zinc and copper ions to the solution did not impact the morphology and distribution of the nanofibers, and highly interconnected networks of fibers with varying diameters were observed.

Figure 2 presents the values obtained for the fiber diameter, categorized by composition. It can be observed that, for each composition, there is a decrease in the average diameter of the nanofibers after the HT. This phenomenon has been documented in a previous study by Ju *et al* [22]. When studying 70Si–30Ca compositions, the authors found diameters of 329 ± 32 nm and 199 ± 20 nm before and after HT, respectively [22]. This behavior is attributed to the removal of the PVB as a binding polymer. However, in this case, the decrease is not as pronounced, which could be attributed to the amount of PVB utilized [8]. It was found that the higher the concentration of the binding polymer, the greater was the reduction in diameter following the calcination process.

Additionally, compositions containing Cu (80Si–18Ca–2Cu or 80Si–15Ca–5Cu) exhibited larger diameters compared to nanofibers with Zn (80Si–18Ca–2Zn or 80Si–15Ca–5Zn). This result could be attributed to the fact that more attached fibers were

present in the Cu samples, leading to an increase in the average size analyzed by the software. The measurement error in diameter arises from the challenge of distinguishing between a single fiber and two attached fibers based on the viewing angle. However, all compositions fall within the range of approximately 500–700 nm, which aligns with reported similar fibrous scaffold types [16, 23].

Homogeneous cotton wool-like scaffolds were mostly achieved for all compositions, with occasional bead formation and smooth fibers of varying diameters. Furthermore, some fibers were observed to adhere to each other even after the calcination HT. These findings are consistent with previous literature reports that employed similar components for scaffold production [5, 8]. (See Supplementary information for all SEM images of each composition before and after HT).

3.3. ATR-FTIR characterization

ATR-FTIR spectra for each cotton wool-like scaffold composition before HT are displayed in figure 3(A). The Si–OH (960 – 950 cm^{-1} and 795 – 805 cm^{-1}) and Si–O–Si (1145 – 1135 cm^{-1} and 1070 – 1060 cm^{-1}) functional groups correspond to the specific type of silicate BG produced [5, 16]. The presence of C–H groups (1420 – 1410 cm^{-1} and 1330 – 1320 cm^{-1}) is attributed to the PVB polymer, while the O–H vibrational groups (3330 – 3320 cm^{-1} and 1640 – 1630 cm^{-1}) are indicative of residual water and solvents (ethanol). Upon initial inspection, it can be observed that the peak positions remain consistent across all samples. The results indicated that including zinc and copper ions did not induce changes in the functional groups of the cotton wool-like scaffolds. However, slight variations in peak intensities

Figure 3. ATR-FTIR spectra of (A) cotton wool-like scaffolds before HT, and (B) 80Si-20Ca scaffolds before and after HT. (The relevant peaks are discussed in the text, section 2.3).

are evident, which may be attributed to the varying amounts of functional groups per unit volume in the measured samples. Figure 3(B) compares 80Si-20Ca samples before and after HT. As expected, in the treated sample, the peaks associated with PVB, water, and other solvents were no longer detectable, indicating their complete disappearance during the HT process. This result could confirm the effective removal of these components from the sample through calcination. All compositions showed

comparable peaks after HT (see supplementary information).

3.4. EDX characterization

In general, all compositions exhibited the presence of the expected chemical elements. Figure 4 displays the elemental peaks for the 80Si-10Ca-5Zn-5Cu composition. Peaks corresponding to Si, Ca, and O, which are characteristic of bioactive Si-Ca glasses, are observed. Additionally, peaks for copper and zinc

Figure 4. EDX results for 80Si-10Ca-5Zn-5Cu scaffold.

confirm the presence of these ions in the nanofibers. The variation in peak intensity between samples may be attributed to the measurement position, as the distribution of elements is not necessarily uniformly homogeneous throughout the fibrous structure.

The color mapping in figure 5 illustrates the spatial distribution of elements for the 80Si-10Ca-5Zn-5Cu composition. Generally, the distribution appears qualitatively relatively homogeneous, with some areas exhibiting higher concentrations of certain elements and other regions with lower presence of them. Similar distribution patterns were observed for the other compositions, and no significant differences were detected among the samples.

3.5. Ion release

The release of Ca, Si, Cu, and Zn ions was quantified by immersing cotton wool-like nanofibers in 5 mM TRIS buffer (pH 7.5) for different incubation periods and subsequently analyzing them using ICP-OES (with Varian Vista MPX instrument), as shown in figure 6. Different detection limits (DL) were defined for each ion. Figure 6(A) demonstrates a notable increase in the expected release of Ca ions over time during incubation. It is evident that only compositions containing Ca in their formulation exhibit significant release of this ion, except for 80Si-15Ca-5Zn and 80Si-10Ca-5Zn-5Cu, where the release was below the DL. This result is expected since the nominal compositions contain less amount of Ca compared to the parent composition due to the fact that the incorporation of doping elements was done via

substitution of Ca. The higher amount of doping could cause structural changes as it may lead to higher network connectivity.

In figure 6(B), release of Si is observed for all compositions after 7 d of incubation. An expected increase in release is also noted with increasing incubation time and the release of Si was observed in all sample compositions. The highest release of Si was detected in the 80Si-18Ca-2Zn composition at the 4 h incubation period, however, with increasing incubation time, the detected Si release was higher in the parent (or base) composition compared to the other samples. In general, the concentration of soluble Si decreases with increasing Zn doping in the glass structure. On the other hand, similar behavior was not observed in the case Cu doping: Si release was comparable in 80Si-18Ca-2Cu and 80Si-15Ca-5Cu. It is interesting to note that similar observations were reported in other articles. For example, the incorporation of Zn and Cu into 58S glass composition caused a lower degradation and higher stability of glasses, and this effect was more prominent in the case of Zn containing glasses over Cu containing glasses [24]. This behavior was attributed to the role of Zn in the glass structure: ZnO can act as either a network modifier or an intermediate oxide in the glass structure. It has been reported that in high amount, ZnO acts as an intermediate oxide leading to formation of covalent bonds between SiO₂ tetrahedron resulting in a stable structure [13]. When considering the increase of doping elements concentration (80Si-16Ca-2Zn-2Cu vs 80Si-10Ca-5Zn-5Cu), the Si release decreased gradually. The lowest Si release was detected in the

80Si–10Zn–10Cu sample, which supports the hypothesis that the network connectivity of the glasses increased with doping.

Furthermore, figure 6(C) illustrates the release of Cu from the cotton wool-like nanofibers. Cu release was not detected at 4 h of incubation, whereas a high concentration of Cu was observed at day 1 in the case of the highest Cu containing BG. Additionally, after 7 d of incubation, noticeable Cu release was observed from samples containing Cu such as 80Si–18Ca–2Cu, 80Si–16Ca–2Zn–2Cu, 80Si–15Ca–5Cu, and 80Si–10Ca–5Zn–5Cu. However, Cu release from the 80Si–10Zn–10Cu sample was not detected. The reason for this behavior is likely that the network modifier amount decreases because the composition does not contain calcium and, at the higher zinc amounts, ZnO can act as intermediate oxide which may lead to a more compact network, as discussed before (evidenced by a reduced Si release by the same glass composition). On the other hand, the effect of CuO on the glass network connectivity is likely small [25]. The release of Zn was not detected in none of the samples which contain Zn. It needs to be highlighted that this result does not necessarily implies low Zn release from the BGs, but it is possible that Zn could form Zn-Tris complexes/compounds.

In fact, it has been reported that Zn could form stable complexes with Tris at pH 8 [26], as elevated pH levels are known to be caused by BGs.

3.6. Antibacterial test

The results of the antibacterial test using AlamarBlue reduction assay against *E.coli* as a gram-negative and *S. aureus* as a gram-positive bacteria are presented in figure 7. Figure 7(A) demonstrates that the reductions in AlamarBlue are more significant at lower ion concentrations, indicating that increasing the amount of Zn and Cu leads to a reduction in bacterial activity. Previous studies have confirmed the effectiveness of Zn and Cu ions as antibacterial agents, widely used in various biomedical applications [27, 28]. Moreover, it can be observed that there is a distinction between 80Si–20Ca scaffolds and compositions containing Zn and Cu ions, particularly at higher concentrations of these ions. However, no significant differences are observed between compositions that include Zn versus those with Cu. Additionally, figure 7(B) illustrates that the antibacterial response for *S. aureus* bacteria remains relatively stable as the amount of Zn and Cu ions increases. Once again, compositions including Zn and/or Cu exhibited better antibacterial outcomes than 80Si–20Ca.

Figure 8. Images showing *S. aureus* colonies for (A) 80Si–20Ca and (B) 80Si–10Zn–10Cu.

On the other hand, Zn and Cu are well-known ions for their antibacterial activity [12, 27, 28]. For instance, Cu ions can bind to the cell membrane, damaging its structural integrity. This disruption weakens membrane permeability, resulting in the leakage of essential ions and molecules, compromising cell viability [12, 28]. In the case of Zn ions, they can also disrupt bacterial membranes through different mechanisms such as interfering with membrane-associated enzymes and proteins, thereby destabilizing the membrane structure [12, 27]. Therefore, this study anticipated that the combined effects of Zn and Cu against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* would result in enhanced antibacterial properties due to their individual and complementary actions. However, there was no significant difference between the Zn, Cu, or Zn/Cu samples. The lack of difference could be attributed to the high dose of individual ions, meaning that the incorporation of Zn and Cu already had a high impact on bacterial viability reduction.

Additionally, figure 8 compares bacterial growth using solid agar plates for the 80Si–20Ca and 80Si–10Zn–10Cu compositions. It is evident that there is a higher presence of bacterial colonies when Zn or Cu ions are absent in the sample, whereas a noticeable reduction is observed when these ions are present. These findings are consistent with previous analysis regarding Zn and Cu antibacterial behavior [14, 29].

3.7. *In vitro* cytotoxicity assay

The viability and growth of HaCaT cells were evaluated by WST-8 colorimetric assay to study the *in vitro* biocompatibility of all cotton wool-like scaffold compositions incubated for 48 h, as shown in figure 9. Cell viability higher than 80% is accepted as non-toxic, according to ISO-10993-5 [19]. Based on this standard, cotton wool-like electrospun nanofibers with or without Zn and Cu showed non-cytotoxic behavior compared to the control group. It is well-known from previous studies that the cytotoxicity of Cu- or Zn-doped glasses depends on the ion concentration [30–33]. In our case, both Cu-doped and Zn-doped cotton wool-like electrospun fibers were not toxic, which

could be due to the relatively low release of ions. This behaviour correlates with the ion release results discussed in section 2.6. On the other hand, figure 9 illustrates that 80Si–15Ca–5Cu, although it has no toxic effect on HaCaT cells, exhibits lower cell viability compared to 80Si–15Ca–5Zn and 80Si–10Ca–5Zn–5Cu cotton-wool-like fibers. It is well-known that Zn and Cu can interact antagonistically in cellular environments [12]. For instance, Zn ions may compete with Cu ions for binding sites on enzymes or cell membranes, thereby reducing the cytotoxic effects of Cu [12, 34]. This competition can prevent Cu from exerting damaging effects on cellular components [12, 34]. In the present study, the difference in HaCaT cell viability could be due to the combination of Zn and Cu, which may decrease HaCaT cell viability through antagonistic interactions, protective roles of Zn against oxidative stress and synergistic effects.

3.8. *In vitro* wound healing assay

The wound scratch assay is a cost-effective standard method used to mimic 2D wound healing and investigate cell migration in *in vitro* conditions by making a scratch in a confluent cell monolayer [35]. In the current study, cotton wool-like electrospun nanofibers were evaluated with the method of *in vitro* wound scratching assay using HaCaT cells. The wound closure rate of the cotton wool-like electrospun nanofibers after 4 h and 24 h incubation is presented in figure 10. After the 24 h incubation, HaCaT wound closure results showed that all compositions (except 80Si–15Ca–5Cu composition) exhibited high wound closure. However, for the 80Si–15Ca–5Cu composition, a value close to 80% was obtained, which indicated a significant difference in cell migration. Previous studies have reported that both ions (Zn and Cu) could enhance wound healing by recruiting keratinocyte cells towards migration and proliferation [36, 37]. Furthermore, *in vivo* studies have demonstrated that the interaction with Cu accelerated granulation tissue formation and neovascularization [38]. However, the current study confirms that doping Cu

or Zn into cotton wool-like electrospun fibers does not have a cytotoxic effect on HaCaT cells, nor does it impede cell migration. Consistent with our results, in a similar study, Cu-doped BG fibers did not inhibit HaCaT cell migration [16].

4. Conclusions

Successful fabrication of cotton wool-like scaffolds doped with zinc and copper ions was achieved. The scaffolds exhibited a predominantly 3D architecture

with a cotton wool-like appearance. SEM observations revealed interconnected networks of homogeneous and bead-free nanofibers, although occasional beads and fiber entanglement were observed. These defects were attributed to the electrospinning parameters and solution preparation times, affecting solution viscosity. Furthermore, the average diameter of the nanofibers decreased after the calcination HT, attributed to the removal of the polymer binding agent. EDX analysis confirmed the presence of expected chemical elements and showed mostly

homogeneous spatial distribution of the elements based on color maps.

The antibacterial properties of the scaffolds, particularly due to the presence of zinc and copper ions, were analyzed. The results indicated good antibacterial effects, with reduced bacterial activities observed as the concentration of these ions increased. Cell viability results showed a non-toxic characteristic for all compositions on HaCaT cells. Additionally, *in vitro* wound healing assay results indicated that cotton wool-like electrospun nanofibers with Zn and Cu exhibited a high wound closure rate. The evidence from this study implies, therefore, that incorporating Zn and Cu into cotton wool-like BG nanofibers is a powerful approach to enhance the scaffold's antibacterial and biological activity. These scaffolds can potentially prevent wound infection and enhance wound closure during wound healing, being thus interesting bioactive systems for ionic medicine applications.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

Acknowledgments

I H R thanks the IDEAR (Germany-Argentina Engineers) program from DAAD (German Academic Exchange Service) for the internship opportunity at FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg. This paper is part of the dissemination activities of the project FunGlass. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No: 739566.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: I H R, L L, I U, G A A, and A R B, methodology: I H R, L L, I U and N M, formal analysis: I H R, I U, and N M, investigation: I H R, L L, I U, N M, M M, G A A and A R B, resources: A R B; data curation: I H R, I U, L L, and N M, writing-original draft preparation: I H R, and I U, writing-review and editing: I H R, L L, I U, N M, M M, G A A and A R B, visualization: I H R, I U, L L, and N M, supervision: G A A and A R B, project administration: A R B.

Conflict of interest

The authors whose names are listed certify that they have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest

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